

USE OF INTERNET - RESOURCES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Annotation: This article discusses the relevance of the use of modern Internet technologies in teaching a foreign language, and also analyzes the importance and effectiveness of using web technologies in learning a foreign language.

Keywords: Internet resources, communication technologies, Internet technologies, multimedia tools, social networks.

In recent years, in the field of teaching foreign languages, the question of the importance and expediency of using Internet resources in foreign language education has been increasingly raised, which implies not only an analysis of the use of new technical means, but also a study of the positive and negative aspects of introducing innovative forms and methods of teaching.

Modern methods of teaching foreign languages are associated with ongoing technical progress, as well as with the technological renewal of the learning process. The latest achievements in the field of high technologies and the spread of the global Internet open up the widest opportunities for foreign language teachers, methodologists, as well as the students themselves to further improve the educational process.

Undoubtedly, the Internet can be used as an effective application for the development of grammatical, lexical skills and abilities, knowledge testing. This includes all kinds of training lexical, grammar, phonetic exercises, reading tests, grammar, IQ tests, etc. Teachers or students themselves can find such sites on the WWW.

A big plus of using Internet resources is the development of intercultural competence, i.e., getting to know different cultures, determining the ways of their interaction and interpenetration into each other, the formation of cultural universals necessary to achieve mutual understanding and fruitful cooperation in direct communication.

World Wide The Web with a huge number of sites and home pages providing information for all tastes is an endless field of activity in terms of using a foreign language in a foreign language lesson to develop intercultural competence.

You can invite students to travel as tourists or guides. They will be able to pack the luggage themselves and recommend the necessary things to their clients, call the contact numbers of airlines and hotels to get information about the availability of tickets and vacancies, fill out forms for obtaining a visa and passport. As a report on the work done, you can invite students to create a photo album or diary of their travels.

The WILD-e site offers for consideration the aspects of mastering and the problems of the profession of a teacher teaching a foreign language. Here you can read current statements and share your own if you wish, explore the world of metaphors, give your own answers in the heading "Tell me why?" (Can you tell me why ?) to questions of interest to everyone, such as "Why are people allowed to write theoretical treatises on pedagogy who have nothing to do with teaching practice?" ("Why are there so many things about teaching and educational administration that are so pointless and stupid?"), share experience last lesson and t . d .

Thus, using the information resources of the Internet, it is possible, integrating them into the educational process, to more effectively solve a number of didactic tasks in an English lesson:

a) to form reading skills and abilities, directly using the materials of the network of varying degrees of complexity;

listening skills on the basis of authentic Internet audio texts, also prepared by the teacher accordingly;

c) improve the skills of monologue and dialogic utterance on the basis of a problematic discussion presented by the teacher or one of the students, network materials;

d) improve writing skills, individually or in writing compiling answers to partners, participating in the preparation of abstracts, essays, and other epistolary products of joint activities of partners;

e) replenish their vocabulary, both active and passive, with the vocabulary of modern English, reflecting a certain stage in the development of the culture of the people, the social and political structure of society.

When working with computer technologies, the role of the teacher also changes, whose main task is to support and guide the development of the personality of students, their creative search. Relations with students are built on the principles of cooperation and joint creativity.

The use of Internet resources in foreign language lessons and in extracurricular activities has a number of undeniable advantages, in particular, it increases the cognitive activity and motivation of students, ensures a higher quality of the learning process and independent activities of students, since students spend a lot of time in the virtual world and are more willing to learn information disseminated in social networks and mobile applications. The latest multimedia and Internet technologies help to quickly and effectively master the perception of oral speech, put the correct pronunciation, learn grammar rules, master fluent reading and deep understanding of authentic texts, create real communication situations, remove psychological barriers and increase interest in the language. All this is the most important task of teaching a foreign language to improve already acquired skills and develop new ones.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the use of Internet resources and multimedia tools gives teachers an excellent opportunity to improve learning management, increase the efficiency and objectivity of the educational process, save the teacher's time, increase students' motivation to gain knowledge, interest them in learning foreign languages, instill a strong desire for self-control and self-improvement, which will positively affect learning outcomes.

Literature:

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